

51. Timber-regionality and temporality in Northern Europe's shipbuilding resource

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Introduction

A great wealth of tree-ring data now exists for oak ships found across Northern Europe, due to the exercise of dating these timbers and, not least, determining their region of origin. This has allowed links between diverse regions to be made, and to see, in this material evidence, patterns of communication growing and changing through time. An even greater wealth of tree-ring data, for oak in Northern Europe, from our terrestrial

built heritage provides the tool which we use for dating and locating the source of ships' timbers. I am beginning to tap into this dendrochronological resource, through analysis of timber size, age and growth rate, to try to attain a picture of the availability of the timber resource for shipbuilding, through time and space. Through collaboration between dendrochronologists a great volume of this dataset is available for research, allowing comparison of tree-ring data across regions.

Fig. 1. Map showing the distribution of correlation (t-values) when a mean of tree-ring widths for the AD 1539 building phase of Stirling Castle, Scotland (Crone, 2008) is compared to site chronologies for a range of structures throughout Northern Europe (Map: Aoife Daly).

Timber growth rate

One of the details that can be extracted from these tree-ring data concerns the rate at which different trees grew, over time and space. Annual variation in the tree-ring widths is determined by the annually fluctuating climate at the location where the tree is growing, producing a dateable tree-ring pattern. However an individual tree, depending on how much competition it has, for light, from neighbouring trees, might grow at a quite slow rate in a dense forest but grow relatively quickly in a more open landscape. We can therefore use the average ring widths of individual trees, extracted from our dendrochronological dataset, as a suggested proxy for the degree of the tree coverage over time. A few years ago, in connection with dendro-archaeological analysis of the Mollö ship, SW Sweden, I experimented with this, by carrying out an analysis of the growth rate of oak timbers used in ships from Northern Europe (Arbin & Daly, 2012). Combining the date of the ship with the provenance of the timbers and the average ring width, it was clear that the story of the requisition of oak for ship-building is not a simple chronological one. Rather, it is strongly related to different regions experiencing shortage of this resource at different periods in time, leading to a necessity for importing timber. This is very clear for instance in the case of Scotland. Dendrochronological analyses, including dating and provenance determination, of timbers from many historic buildings throughout Scotland shows that native Scottish oak is utilised until around 1450 (Crone & Mills, 2012). The condition of the native oak by this time indicates that the resource is running out, and after this date building timber is imported, chiefly from Scandinavia. First oak and later pine appears in the Scottish material.

Now as we move into the 16th century, identifying just where in Scandinavia this traded timber was acquired becomes problematical. In fig. 1 a map shows the results of testing the region of origin for timbers from one of the building phases from Stirling Castle in Scotland. The analysis of the building was carried out by Anne Crone (Crone, 2008). The symbols on the map indicate the t-value achieved when we tested the correlation (t-value) between the average for the timbers from episode 3, dating to AD 1539, and site chronologies from Northern Europe (for a detailed description of the methodology see: Daly, 2007a and 2007b). The map shows clearly that the oaks for this phase at Stirling Castle had grown in Southern Scandinavia, but the high correlation with many sites throughout Denmark leads to the question, how widespread the trade and transport of timber was in the Southern Scandinavian region at this time? Is the phenomenon of many high t-values in this map a product of the contamination, if that's not too strong a word to use, of the terrestrial tree-ring dataset by imports?

Other questions that can be asked are: is the Scottish story of a dwindling resource repeated in other regions?

If so, when do we see the trade of oak timber begin, what proportion of timber is imported and what proportion is native? When we find imported timber in the material we highlight it, because it tells an interesting story, and thus we as researchers might tend to increase the visibility of timber transport in publication. For this reason it is the aim of this paper to interrogate the terrestrial dendrochronological dataset, to try to balance the story.

Timber source over time

While we now have extensive tree-ring data from our built and archaeological heritage, it is a very time consuming task to unravel some of the details of the oak timber resource story. For this exploratory research, I have for several reasons concentrated primarily on data for Denmark and covering almost two millennia. The vast majority of data are accumulated by myself through nearly 20 years of working as a dendro-archaeologist, but some additional data are included that were generated by the Danish National Museum and the WM Trædateringslaboratoriet, that were kindly made available, during my PhD studies some years ago. It is not a fully complete set of all tree-ring data from Denmark but might rather be considered a random sample (dendrochronological data have an intrinsic bias in that they represent the usage of long-lived trees, due to the requirement of long tree-ring series for successful analysis. So the younger, more readily renewable underwood is heavily underrepresented, and this might be borne in mind). These data were cleaned to rule out samples that show that their growth might have been affected by the cockchafer beetle (again this is described in: Daly, 2007a), and was also checked for duplicates. After this filtering, a dataset of 1692 tree-ring series remains. As the possibility that structures were made using a mix of local and imported timber I have tested each series individually, to determine whether it is from a native oak, or had grown outside Denmark. When a tree-ring series shows very high correlation with chronologies from Northern Poland, Germany or France we can confidently suggest that this is an import. It is much more problematical though when the highest correlations are with adjacent SW Sweden. In this case, the series in question need to show a high correlation with sites from that region, and a correspondingly low correlation with the Danish dataset. There are instances where a series achieved correlation with such a wide geographical spread of datasets, that its provenance remains a mystery.

Through this exercise I have found that the provenance of 14 series could not be determined, 1342 series could be called local, meaning their provenance is within Denmark while 230 could be imports. There are in addition 106 barrel components in the Danish dataset, none of which are native oak. Of course the huge advantage of dendrochronological data is that they are precisely

Diagram 1. The distribution, through time, of locally sourced timber versus exotic timber in the dendrochronological record for Denmark. Dating is shown on the x-axis, while the y-axis is the average tree-ring width of the samples. It is used here to show the average growth rate of each tree, as a proxy indicator for tree/forest density (Diagram: Aoife Daly).

dated, so we can see how the local versus the imported timber behaves over time. In diagram 1 the result of this analysis is summarised. The X-axis represents years AD, while the Y-axis is the average ring width, expressed in 100ths of a mm. The purple chevrons represent the locally derived timber and clearly there seems to have been an availability of local oak for building throughout, in sharp contrast to the situation in Scotland. It is very interesting to see then that the imported timber (shown in orange) dominates in later centuries, with the odd occurrence as early as the 13th century but particularly abundant from around 1400 onwards, very similar to the Scottish timing for import of oak timber from Scandinavia.

Local timber availability

In diagram 1 the local and imported timber is plotted in relation to the rate of growth of each tree, expressed by the average ring width of each series. At the point where we see a marked increase in the usage of imported oak the average growth rate of the local trees seems faster. The local oaks from the 15th century grow generally faster than in earlier centuries. Just as the Scottish evidence suggests that shortage of native oak timber, from around 1450, necessitates imports, the Danish tree-ring evidence seems to suggest that the intensity of timber exploitation is necessitating the use of trees from more open landscapes, coupled with slower-grown imported timber. Is this because of a shortage of trees from dense forests, or does it reflect an increasing control of forestry? Certainly already in the late 14th century we have clear evidence that younger trees are used for building

in Denmark. A fortified site at Boringholm in Jutland dating to AD 1370 and 1380 (Eriksen, 2000; Daly, 2005) was built with trees less than 80 years old. In contemporary sites of higher status however, trees felled in AD 1400 older than 170 years were used in the castle at Nyborg on the island of Funen (Daly, 2007a: 209-212). It will be interesting in the future when we can interrogate the data at a more detailed level, to look at the context of the timbers that are plotted here. What is the status of buildings that contain imported timber? Does imported timber only appear in urban contexts, or do we see imports in rural construction?

Proportion of local versus exotic

Taking the dataset as a whole just over 17% only of the timbers in this dataset from Denmark might be imports. However this is over a period of 18 centuries. The bar diagram (diagram 2) shows a summary of the frequency of native versus exotic oak timbers through time, grouped by century. Clearly local timber sources dominate in the material through many centuries, but by the 16th century and onwards we see almost equal amounts of local and imported timber in the terrestrial dendrochronological dataset. It is therefore no longer a surprise that the map for Stirling Castle's AD 1539 phase (fig. 1) shows such a wide spread of high correlation with sites in Denmark. Clearly this makes it difficult to pinpoint the origin of these timbers more precisely, but since for this paper I have checked each and every single tree-ring series in my database for provenance and identified those that are probably imports, it is now possible to see that the dataset that the Stirling timbers match best with are

Diagram 2. The number of timbers of local vs. exotic origin in a tree-ring dataset for Denmark, grouped by century (Diagram: Aoife Daly).

the timbers that are probably not native to Denmark, but are imports from Southwest Sweden.

As is made clear here, the information to be gained from interrogating the enormous tree-ring dataset, even in this relatively small case study is producing some very interesting information. To draw additional insightful conclusions will require further study however, particularly to examine the archaeological or building context of the timbers in the data, to identify where in the built environment the imported timbers were used.

The material evidence for timber trade through the chronological and geographical precision that dendrochronology provides allows a very detailed picture of the history of the trade in timber throughout Northern Europe. The trade in so-called 'Baltic' timber has dominated this story, where trade of panelling, wainscots, barrel staves among others has taken place and the tree-ring evidence for this has been extensively documented (Baillie *et al.*, 1985; Eckstein *et al.*, 1986; Hiram & Tyers, 1995; Ważny, 2002; Klein, 2003). Plank cargoes have even been found in shipwrecks and an example of this is the precisely dated Skjernøysund 3 wreck and cargo (Auer & Maarleveld, 2013). The ship itself is made from timber felled in the winter of AD 1389-90 while her cargo is from winter AD 1393-94, and both the ship's timbers and the cargo are of a Southern Baltic origin (Daly, 2011). One of the big questions that I have been working on as a dendro-archaeologist concerns the dating and

provenance of timbers from shipwrecks. For how long, in Northern Europe, are ships built in the region where the timber is felled, and when do we see the material evidence for transport of timber in ships, to a shipbuilding site elsewhere? The suggested turning point for the growth in the transport of bulk oak timber might be c. 1400, as an analysis of a range of case studies has indicated (Daly, 2007a: 218-225). As additional wrecks come to light and are analysed, this picture is continually being refined and new data are added. This paper about terrestrial tree-ring data shows particularly Sweden but also Norway and Northern Germany as sources for construction timber in Denmark.

So in this short paper, I hope I have been able to show that even through a relatively small self-contained study of one region of Northern Europe new insights into some of the questions of oak supply in the region can emerge. I certainly think this demonstrates the potential of interrogating this extensive dataset. One of the lessons learned is that the enormous dataset must be interrogated regionally, to see patterns in timber usage, particularly when trying to use tree-rings as proxy indicators for forest density. Future research in accord with this line of enquiry will enable a description of the regionality of resource depletion versus abundance, and will draw us towards some explanations of the dynamics of the patterns of the maritime timber trade that we see emerging, over time, in Northern Europe.

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